

EUPHEMISMS AND THEIR PLACE IN THE FRAMEWORK OF RELATED LANGUAGE PHENOMENA

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This article talks about how euphemisms differ from similar phenomena at the linguistic level, and what tasks these phenomena perform in linguistics and their differences from euphemisms. Through this, it is possible to clarify what kind of linguistic element euphemisms are and for what purposes they are used by people on the basis of research carried out in modern linguistics.

In distinguishing euphemisms studied by many scholars from other similar, even sometimes synonymous phenomena, E.S. The distinction can be made through the following linguistic criteria endorsed by Glios (Glios: 2007, 8):

- 1) nalichie tematcheski stigmatichnogo nekorrektnogo antecedenta,
- 2) there is a pragmatic reason behind the lack of a tool,
- 3) cosvennost, opisatelnost, meliorativnost, periphrasticnost euphemism,
- 4) the implementation is a simple euphemistic function.

Agreeing with the opinion of the author who stated that it is possible to distinguish euphemisms by these criteria, it can be added that the main goal of using modern euphemisms is to correctly implement the pragmatic intention of the communicator during the conversation with a certain person. This situation is especially evident in the process of dialogue on inter-national and inter-cultural political, economic and cultural topics.

When we get acquainted with the works of world scientists on this issue, it should be noted that taboo words and euphemisms are often mentioned side by side. According to A.A.Reformatsky, euphemisms are used instead of taboos caused by heresy and superstition (Kadirova: 2012, 10). From this point of view, it can be understood that euphemisms are found, that is, they serve to eliminate the words that cause discomfort in the communication between people, to make the opinion positive.

Schroeder, expressing Shorkh's thoughts in his scientific research, offers three ways to distinguish between euphemism and taboos: a) taboo and euphemism can be synonymous in some cases; b) taboos and euphemisms are not synonymous with each other, but are considered at the same level/parallel phenomenon; c) if the elements prohibiting the use of a word or a lexical unit in the language are taboo, then a word or a combination of words used in its place is a euphemism. Schorch considers the third way to clearly show the difference between the two terms and points out that euphemisms are not limited to the function of being used in place of taboos (Schröder: 2016, 9).

Differentiating euphemistic units from the thousands of units that exist in every language is also one of the important issues. N.I. Gaybullaeva puts forward the following

criteria in this regard: 1) widespread euphemism; 2) methodological characteristics; 3) metaphorical nature of the nomination; 4) pleasantness and pleasantness; 5) having a euphemistic character; 6) common connection of euphemisms with linguistic phenomena (Gaybullaeva: 2019, 11).

Agreeing with the opinion put forward by N.M. Berdova, it should be noted that in the occurrence of euphemisms, socially unacceptable acceptance of a certain denotation is of great importance. In such a case, the speaker uses a word with a positive influence instead of this denotation. This process is frequently encountered in the intercultural communication of our globalized era (Berdova: 1980, 29). So it is clear that the study of euphemisms does not lose its relevance.

A.N. Prudyvus examines euphemistic nominalizations in German and notes that euphemism differs from nominalization in its positive or neutral evaluative connotations (Prudyvus: 2006, 9). So euphemisms cannot have a negative meaning within their semantic framework. Euphemisms are the best way to overcome awkwardness and processes that prevent positive communication between speakers.

The scientist emphasizes that the process of euphemization occurs at all levels of stylistics, that euphemisms can be made from all stylistic figures and tropes, and divides them into three groups: euphemisms of high, neutral, and reduced style. He also notes that modern euphemism is characterized by a tendency to intensively use euphemisms of a reduced style. It is also important that Prudyvus explains the difference between euphemism and naming as follows: that is, the only similarity between euphemism and naming is negative denotative correlation. A euphemism differs from a direct naming by expressing its indirect positive or neutral value connotation (Prudyvus: 2006, 10). Therefore, euphemisms neutralize or make positive the transmission of negative information and thereby eliminate the discomfort between the speakers during the conversation. It seems that by using euphemisms, people try to convey a positive message as much as possible to the interlocutor in the process of communication. For this purpose, euphemisms are widely used in spoken and written speech and it can be seen that they have not lost their relevance in the current global era. Because the study of euphemisms has been in the scope of scientific research even in the 21st century.

G.N. In her research, Mukhamedyanova compared and studied euphemisms in German, Russian and Bashkir languages and explained the different aspects of euphemisms from related phenomena in the language. He included amelioration, cryptolalia, and disinformation phenomena in phenomena close to euphemism (Mukhamedyanova: 2005, 4), and explained their similar and different functions to euphemisms.

Melioration (lat. "melioration" - improvement) is used instead of a word, like euphemisms, and serves to have a positive effect on the conveyed meaning, but in the process of melioration, the word being replaced does not negate the word being replaced, that is, euphemisms are a certain taboo in the process of communication between people in society. if it is used instead of the existing word and serves to have a positive effect, a concept that is prohibited to be used in the process of melioration is not denied. Although the phenomenon of two languages also serves to expand the range of positive influence of a concept, euphemisms are a phenomenon that is used instead of words that cannot be said, and which create an uncomfortable situation if they are said (Mukhamedyanova: 2005, 13).

The author compares the phenomena of euphemism and cryptolalia and expresses the following opinions:

“Euphemia and cryptolalia are differentiated phenomena that reveal similarities in structural organization. (...) Euphemia seeks ways to obscure undesirable semantic components determined by the action of moral restrictions. Unlike euphemism, cryptolalia allows for the absence of a referential connection between the antecedent and the secondary nomination, however, an essential condition for concealing the essence of the denoted is the compliance of the replaced word with the criterion of the truth of the statement (Mukhamedyanova: 2005, 13).”

It should also be noted that cryptolalia also serves to mitigate the situation, but the main purpose of its use is to maintain secrecy. Some words used in military linguistics can be given as an example. Although both phenomena serve the same purpose in some cases, the main function of euphemism differs from cryptolalia in that it eliminates an awkward situation in speech and thus creates a neutral or positive impression.

Nowadays, political and economic relations are rapidly developing due to the process of communication between nations due to globalization. It is in these areas that the purpose of choosing one word instead of another is to find the right way in relation to another nation or its representative. Euphemisms serve this purpose in oral and written speech in political processes. The phenomenon of disinformation is also used by political scientists, in this phenomenon we can see that one word is used instead of another word. But the concept of disinformation is defined as a deliberate distortion of the truth, a misinterpretation of the principle of accuracy or truthfulness. This phenomenon greatly complicates the process of decoding the semantic content, as it breaks the content, the referential connection between the prototype and the secondary denomination. Through the phenomenon of disinformation, existing discomfort, sometimes even fear, is eliminated, and in this respect it is a process close to the function of euphemism. However, due to the fact that the main purpose of this event is to hide the truth in the information, we cannot call them a full-fledged euphemism (Mukhamedyanova: 2005, 17).

It is known that many euphemisms are used in fiction. But they differ from paraphrases (litota, hyperbola, metaphor and other stylistic elements) used by authors to beautify the speech of texts. The difference of euphemisms from the stylistic groups listed above is that they are not only aimed at beautifying the text through the chosen expression, attracting the reader's attention, but also are positive or neutral mood-giving elements used by authors instead of words and phrases whose use is unpleasant, unacceptable, shameful or forbidden by society (Glios: 2007, 8-9).

A. J. Omonturdiev, the author of his doctoral dissertation "Professional speech euphemisms", notes that it is difficult to separate euphemisms from related phenomena. According to the author, even proverbs, sayings, aphorisms, riddles, curses are euphemized. Therefore, taking into account that each of the language elements is used for euphemistic purposes, it is necessary to learn the main difference of euphemism from other language elements (Omonturdiev: 2009, 61).

In a word, the level of softness of the connotation in relation to the denotation is a phenomenon of euphemism (Omonturdiev: 2009, 63), that is, a certain situation in the speech is deliberately softened by the informant, brought to a pleasant state.

Finally, it should be emphasized that scientists have different opinions about euphemisms and other similar language elements. Although the above-mentioned linguistic phenomena are similar to euphemisms in some aspects or their functions, they cannot fully reflect the goals that euphemisms set for themselves.

Based on the sources studied by us, it should be noted that euphemisms are used by many specialists in our globalized era. Therefore, the study of semantic-stylistic, pragmatic and linguocultural aspects of this language element poses new tasks for linguists.

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